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Comparing catalyst powders and pellets for microwave assisted biogas reforming

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ABSTRACT

Reactor electrification is a promising technology to reduce carbon dioxide emissions in the chemical industry. Moreover, it allows for more compact reactor design and leads to process intensification. Microwave technology can be used to effectively heat solid catalysts for endothermic reactions with numerous benefits. However, microwave heating is restricted to certain materials only and in most cases new catalyst development is necessary. Whereas many studies focus on microwave assisted catalysis over powder samples, studies on industrial pellets or extrudates are far less common. This study compares microwave-assisted biogas reforming over 5 wt.% Ni/SiC in powder and pellet form (2 mm × 2 mm), tested at different temperatures (750, 800, and 850 °C) and gas flow rates (100, 200, 300, and 400 mL/min). Both forms of the catalyst show good activity, but limited long-term stability. Radial temperature gradients caused by radiation losses through the quartz reactor wall, were measured directly by using a fiber optic temperature sensor located inside the bed center and an IR camera at the reactor wall.

1. Introduction

In the near future renewable electricity from solar and wind will become widely available [1]. This opens pathways to use electricity for chemical energy-intensive processes. Currently chemical reactors are heated by burning fossil fuels, generating large carbon dioxide emissions. These carbon dioxide emissions can be reduced significantly by electrification of the chemical industry. Reactors used for endothermic reactions can in principle be heated by electricity in the form of resistive, microwave or inductive heating.

Hydrogen and syngas are important intermediates for the production of ammonia, methanol and synthetic hydrocarbons (Fischer-Tropsch) and are produced in large quantities. Most hydrogen and syngas are produced by steam reforming of natural gas, a strongly endothermic reaction, requiring reaction temperatures above 900 °C. The heat for this process is provided by burning natural gas in large furnaces. The reaction is limited by heat transfer through the wall and the around the catalyst pellets. Moreover, the furnace operating at such high temperatures requires expensive and short-lasting reactor materials. Haldor-Topsoe has pioneered the development of electrically heated steam reforming [2].

Electrification of steam reforming processes can not only reduce the carbon dioxide emissions, but also reduce the reactor footprint by eliminating the large side-fired furnaces. Process intensification becomes further possible by more efficient catalyst/reactor design. Further reduction in carbon dioxide emissions for hydrogen and syngas production are possible by replacing natural gas by biogas. Biogas is a mixture of mainly methane and carbon dioxide, produced by anaerobic digestion of organic waste matter. Syngas can then be produced directly from biogas through the reaction between methane and carbon dioxide, known as dry reforming of methane [3].

Dry reforming of methane (DRM) is a catalytic process in which methane (CH₄) reacts with carbon dioxide (CO₂) to syngas. This reaction is of great interest due to its potential to convert two major greenhouse gases into valuable chemical feedstocks, making it a promising approach for sustainable energy production and carbon recycling. However, DRM is highly endothermic, requiring significant energy input to reach the temperatures (typically 700–900 °C) necessary for efficient conversion. Advances in catalyst design, such as the development of stable, coke-resistant materials and the incorporation of promoters, have been critical in enhancing catalyst performance and longevity. By optimizing the reaction conditions and developing novel catalytic materials, DRM

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Fig. 1. Experimental set-up for microwave model biogas reforming.

offers a pathway to efficiently produce syngas with a lower hydrogen-to-carbon monoxide ratio, ideal for downstream applications in Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, methanol production, and other industrial processes [4].

Microwave heating is a technique that utilizes electromagnetic radiation in the microwave frequency range (between 300 MHz and 300 GHz, with commercial use limited at 915 MHz or 2.45 GHz) to generate heat directly within materials. This approach contrasts with conventional heating methods, which depend on thermal conduction from an external source, making these processes dependent on the heat transfer between the heat source and the target. In microwave heating, energy is absorbed by the material itself through interactions such as dipolar polarization, ionic conduction, and dielectric loss, where polar molecules and ions align and oscillate in response to the alternating electromagnetic field. This mechanism enables rapid and localized heating, often achieving higher temperatures more quickly and uniformly compared to traditional methods.

Microwave assisted catalytic methane dry reforming reactions have been studied at lab scale [5–22]. Mainly catalyst in powder form have been used, although some studies address honeycomb structured catalysts [18,19]. Catalysts in powder form cannot be used in industrial reactors, as it will result in large pressure drops. Pellets or extrudates in different shapes are usually used in industrial reformers. A few studies using microwave heating have shown that large spherical particles might lead to hot-spots at the contact points between the objects, due to a higher electrical field in these points [23]. Honeycombs have been put forward as the ideal support for microwave assisted catalysis, as it forms a single interconnected object. Recently, Vlachos and coll. pointed out the low catalyst inventory by using honeycombs and they proposed honeycombs filled with catalytic pellets [19,24]. However, due to the small dimensions of the honeycomb channels, typically 1 – 1.5 mm, pressure drop in these configurations might become problematic for industrial applications.

Not all materials are heated efficiently under microwave radiation. For example, alumina, often used as an industrial catalyst support, is difficult to heat up by microwaves to high temperatures needed for reforming reactions. On the other hand, silicon carbide and carbon are excellent microwave-susceptible materials. This makes the correct catalyst material selection essential. Information on the interaction between microwaves and solid materials can be found elsewhere [25]. Recently, Dios Garcia et al. [15] tested a Ni/SiC powder catalyst for methane dry reforming and observed good heating properties as well as good catalytic activity and stability. Shi et al. [20] used a Ni/CeO₂-SiC

and observed an increase of an order of magnitude for the rate of methane dry reforming by microwave heating.

In addition, while using microwave-assisted heating, it is essential not only to carefully choose the material for the catalytic support but also the material for the reactor as well, to guarantee the microwave to pass through it with no power loss. The transparency of quartz reactors enables real-time monitoring of the temperature of the material being heated located close to the reactor wall using either a pyrometer or an infrared (IR) camera. These devices must operate at a wavelength capable of penetrating the quartz reactor wall to ensure accurate temperature readings.

The unique heating mechanism of microwaves—where energy is absorbed from the inside of the material outward—can result in a radial temperature gradient between the bed center and the reactor wall. This phenomenon is enhanced by the high radiative losses through the transparent reactor walls. If not accounted for, this gradient may lead to a significant underestimation of the actual temperature within the reactor core.

This work is part of a larger study aiming at the development of pellet catalysts for the dry reforming of biogas heated by microwaves. For this purpose, a Ni/SiC catalyst was synthesized both as powder and as a 2 mm x 2 mm pellet and tested in a microwave heated reactor under biogas reforming conditions.

2. Experimental

Both heating and catalytic test were performed using a Sairem GMP G3 2k mono-mode magnetron microwave generator, capable to produce plane waves of microwaves with a fixed frequency of 2.45 GHz and a maximum power of 2 kW. It consists of a rectangular waveguide (TE_{1,0} mode, WR340 standard) with an AI4S automatic impedance tuner, as well as a short-circuit slide to adjust the resonant frequency. The short-circuit slide was adjusted to obtain a homogeneous temperature profile across the bed, rather than minimizing completely the reflected power. The cavity has the same width (86.36 mm) and height (43.18 mm) as the waveguide and a length of 115 mm. The chimneys at the top and bottom of the cavity prevent MW from leaking and keep all the energy confined within the cavity. The quartz reactor is introduced through the top and bottom chimneys positioned at the center of the cavity. The monitoring of the temperature is done by three different instruments (for more details see the supporting information).

- An Optris CT 3 M pyrometer to monitor the temperature of the catalyst particles located at the reactor wall in the range 50° - 400 °C
- An Optris CTratio 2ML pyrometer, starting from 275 °C, that has been coupled with a Molex FVP200220240 fused silica fiber optic for the temperature measures inside the catalytic bed (center position) during MW-heating
- An Optris P1 1 M 41°x25° infrared camera to monitor the temperature of the catalyst particles located at the reactor wall starting from 450 °C

Fig. 1 shows an overview of the microwave heated reactor set-up.

The microwave setup used in this study can operate in two different modes, applied at different stages of the experiments.

- **Temperature control mode:** once a temperature setpoint is defined, the system automatically adjusts the microwave power to reach and maintain the desired temperature. This mode is used during the catalyst pre-treatment phase to ensure a slow and controlled reduction of the 5 wt. % Ni/SiC catalyst.
- **Power control mode:** once a power value is selected, the system delivers microwaves at constant power. This mode is used during the catalytic experiments to monitor temperature changes resulting from the endothermic nature of the reaction.

Quartz is usually preferred as reactor tube material in MWH applications due to its very low interaction with the electromagnetic field, relatively high melting temperature (>1600 °C) and inertness. Therefore, we chose a quartz tube as a fixed bed reactor. It consists of a straight tube with an 18 mm inner diameter, a frit to hold the catalyst sample and an inner quartz sheath to insert and slide the optical fiber.

A sufficient amount of material must be placed in the cavity to absorb the incoming microwave energy effectively, the whole reactor volume inside the cavity needs to be filled with a microwave absorbing material. For this reason, the interior of the reactor is filled not only with the 5 wt. % Ni/SiC catalyst, but also with an additional amount of SiC to enhance microwave absorption. In each case, the SiC used as microwave susceptor matches the physical form of the catalytic support (powder or pellets).

During the experiments, the catalyst is positioned in the middle of the reactor, between two layers of SiC used as additional microwave absorbing medium, using the same SiC as the catalyst support (powder or pellets). Loading the reactor with catalyst completely will result in complete methane conversion. In that case the evaluation of the catalyst activity and stability is no longer possible. This "sandwich" configuration allows to vary the amount of catalyst, but keeping the total amount of SiC material constant. Heating experiments under nitrogen flow of the reactor filled with SiC only or in sandwich configuration did not show any significant differences in absorbed microwave power and temperature gradients, indicating that the nickel particle did not affect the results significantly.

A total of 500 mg of catalyst is used in each experiment. In the case of the powder catalyst, the resulting bed thickness was insufficient for accurate temperature measurements; therefore, it was diluted with an additional 500 mg of SiC (same type as the support) to increase the bed height and improve measurement accuracy. Before starting the experiments, the optical fiber is inserted inside the reactor in the center of the catalytic bed. Once placed inside the cavity, the tuning of the instrument is done automatically by the AI4S impedance tuner and then further manually by adjusting the position of the reflector at the end of the waveguide. The tuning is done with the purpose to have a symmetric radial distribution of the temperature in the reactor (for tuning done with minimized reflection see the supporting information).

The catalyst pre-treatment consisted of an in-situ reduction under 100 mL/min of H₂/N₂ (1:1 molar ratio), starting from 350 °C till 650 °C at 5 °C/min and then 1 hour at 650 °C. Before starting the dry reforming, the reactor was kept under nitrogen flow, then the forward microwave

Table 1

Operating conditions for the dry reforming experiments.

Parameter	Ni/SiC powder	Ni/SiC pellets
Temperature	750°; 800°; 850 °C	750°; 800°; 850 °C
Gas flow rate	100; 200; 300 mL/min	100; 200; 300; 400 mL/min

Fig. 2. Comparison of the dielectric constant (left axis, blue) and the loss factor (right axis, red) for different SiC materials as a function of temperature. Closed circles: SiC powder 137 μ m, open triangles: SiC pellets (2 mm x 2 mm).

power was regulated in order to get the desired temperature. The reaction started by switching to a mixture of CO₂/CH₄/N₂ (3:1:1 molar ratio). Gas flows were controlled by mass flow controllers (Bronkhorst). The effluent gases were analysed on-line by an Agilent micro-GC 990. It contains modules for the analysis of permanent gases N₂, Ar, He as well as H₂, CH₄, CO₂ and CO. Water was trapped before micro-GC analysis.

Several heating tests have been conducted with our Ni/SiC catalyst (powder and pellets) at different temperatures and gas flow rates, as reported in Table 1.

2.1. Catalyst synthesis

Silicon carbide pellets (β -SiC, SiC4-E2-HP 2 mm pellets from SiCat-ACM, France) in the shape of 2 mm x 2 mm cylinders were used for catalyst synthesis. The SiC pellets have a BET surface area of 26 m²/g. For the pellet catalysts, the SiC pellets were impregnated directly with an aqueous solution of Ni(NO₃)₂, with a calculated amount of salt to have a 5 % in weight of Ni⁰ on the support, then it is dried and calcined for 4 h at 650 °C. For the powder catalyst, the pellets were first grinded in a ball mill, sieved to have a 100–200 μ m particle size and then the same procedure as for the pelletized catalyst was followed.

3. Results and discussion

SiC was used as a support, because of its good microwave-susceptibility, for the nickel-based catalyst. To investigate the microwave behavior of the different SiC materials, the dielectric constant and the loss factor were measured for the SiC powder and the SiC pellets. These two characteristics determine the capacity of a material to store electrical energy and its dissipation into heat. The data are shown in Fig. 2 and confirm the good microwave heating of both materials. Notice that both the dielectric constant and the loss factor change as a function of temperature. Another important factor for heating structured catalysts, is the penetration depth. To obtain uniform heating, the

Fig. 3. Penetration depth as a function of temperature. Closed circles: SiC powder 137 μm , open triangles: SiC pellets (2 mm x 2 mm).

penetration depth should be superior to the dimensions of the object to be heated. Fig. 3 shows the penetration depth for the SiC powder and SiC pellets as a function of temperature. Around 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ the penetration depth for the SiC pellets is around 1 cm, thus allowing uniform heating of the 2 mm x 2 mm pellets (for more details on the dielectric properties measures see the supporting information).

3.1. Microwave tests

Dry reforming experiments were performed at different flow rates at 750, 800 and 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for both the powder and pellet catalysts. The operating temperature refers to the temperature measured by the pyrometer fiber optics in the bed center under nitrogen flow. During dry reforming the temperature of the catalyst will drop, due to the net endothermic reaction.

Fig. 4 shows the methane conversion as a function of the contact time, W/F_{CH_4} . The powder catalyst was more active than the pellets at all temperatures. To get better insight into the difference between the activity for the powder and pellet catalysts, the mass and heat transport

Fig. 4. Catalyst to methane molar flow ratio (W/F_{CH_4}) vs. the methane conversion for different temperatures: 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (red line), 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (green line) and 750 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (blue line) and for different supports: powder (solid line) and pellets (dotted line). The values are recorded after 20 min. of reaction.

limitations were assessed. The details are given in the supporting information and the results are summarized Table S1. For the assessment of the transport limitations, an isothermal reactor was assumed. However, the reactor was far from isothermal conditions during the experiments, as shown by the temperature measurements in the next section. This analysis is still useful to point out where transport limitations are likely to occur. For the powder catalyst no mass and heat transport limitations were revealed. In the case of the pellet support, both external and internal mass transport limitations were indicated. Moreover, severe external heat transfer limitations occurred. The stronger mass and heat transfer limitations observed for the pellets are in line with the lower catalyst activity observed for the 5 wt. % Ni/SiC catalyst pellet. Although no mass and heat transfer limitations are calculated for the powder catalyst, it is difficult to evaluate the true intrinsic rate, as large temperature gradients occur in the reactor, which are discussed in the next section.

Over both catalysts a rather stable methane conversion with time on stream was observed. Fig. 5a shows the methane and carbon dioxide conversion as a function of time on stream for the microwave heated pellets. After an initial drop in activity, the catalyst performance is stable during an hour and a half. After the activity test, thermogravimetric analysis showed the formation of coke. This is not surprising, as the

Fig. 5a. Methane and carbon dioxide conversion (left axis) and H_2/CO ratio (right axis) as a function of time on stream for catalyst pellets in a microwave heated reactor at 850 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Total flow rate of 100 Nml/min.

Fig. 5b. Methane and carbon dioxide conversion (left axis) and H_2/CO ratio (right axis) as a function of time on stream for catalyst pellets in a conventionally heated reactor at $850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Total flow rate of 100 NmL/min .

catalyst formulation is quite simple. Improved stability can be achieved by addition of CeO_2 for example, as demonstrated in Sharifvaghefi et al. [17]. However, long-term stability tests over the same catalyst pellets under the same reaction condition, but using a conventional electric oven to heat the reactor, showed little loss in conversion, see Fig. 5b. Carbon formation is thermodynamically favored at temperatures between $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [26], suggesting that most of the coke formation occurred on the catalysts located close to the reactor wall, where the temperatures were lower than in the center of the reactor. Using a conventional oven, the catalyst located at the reactor wall is hotter than the center temperature where the measurement thermocouple is located. This configuration leads to less coking.

Figs. 6–9 show 2D temperature profiles of the catalyst located at the reactor wall, measured by the IR camera for the experiments at a flow rate of 300 NmL/min at 750 and $850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The experiments at other flow rates and temperatures are available in the supporting information. For each experimental condition, we captured four distinct images:

1. Before the start of the dry reforming experiment (sample under nitrogen flow)

2. After 5 min of reaction (to observe the temperature change induced by the reaction)
3. Towards the end of the dry reforming experiment (to detect any changes that occurred during the reaction)
4. After 5 min back under nitrogen flow (to compare the sample's condition before and after the reaction)

A 5-minute interval was required to ensure that the samples reached thermal equilibrium at the beginning of the reaction and once it is stopped. The Figure legends indicate the temperature of the catalyst at the wall measured by the IR camera ($T_{\text{wall}}^{\circ}(\text{IR})$), the maximum temperature measured by the IR camera ($T_{\text{max}}^{\circ}(\text{IR})$) and the bed center temperature measured by the pyrometer fiber optic ($T_{\text{cent}}^{\circ}(\text{Py})$). The wall temperature was measured at a fixed position close to the middle of the bed, in case of the pellets, corresponding to pellet that touched the reactor wall (see the supporting information). In case of the powder catalyst, the resolution of the IR camera did not allow to take a single particle, but rather a zone on the order of a millimeter. The dotted rectangle indicates both the position of the catalytic bed and the area used to extract the temperature in the powder case.

From these thermal images and temperature measurements, insights into the interaction between microwaves and the different forms of the Ni/SiC catalyst can be extracted. The temperature profiles as measured by the IR camera are rather symmetrical in the axial direction under nitrogen flow. During dry reforming the top part was slightly colder, this is the area where most of the dry reforming reaction occurred. Similarly, a common trend can be identified across all four cases: when switching to reaction conditions, a significant temperature drop occurred due to the high endothermicity of the DRM reaction. This was followed by a return to approximately the initial temperature when the reactant flow was replaced with pure nitrogen at the end of the experiment.

The maximum temperature (T_{max}) measured by the IR camera and the wall temperature (T_{wall}) are the same in the case of the powder catalysts, but quite different for the pellets. The size of the voids between individual pellets was large enough to enable the IR camera to monitor the temperature of pellets located further away from the reactor wall. The temperature of this layer is much higher than the layer located at the reactor wall, because its better shielded from radiation losses. In contrast, the small size of the voids of the powder-filled reactor resulted in a more compact bed, which appeared to the IR camera as a single

Fig. 6. Heating and dry reforming over pellet catalyst at $850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a total flow of 300 mL/min in the microwave heated reactor.

Fig. 7. Heating and dry reforming over pellet catalyst at 750 °C with a total flow of 300 mL/min in the microwave heated reactor.

Fig. 8. Heating and dry reforming over powder catalyst at 850 °C with a total flow of 300 mL/min in the microwave heated reactor.

continuous medium. Thus, in the case of the pellets, due to the hotter inner layers, the average temperature and the maximum temperature read by the IR camera is higher than for the powders. For both catalysts, a large temperature gradient was measured between the center of the bed and the reactor wall under both nitrogen gas and dry reforming conditions. This finding highlights an important aspect of microwave-assisted catalysis: relying solely on wall temperature measurements is insufficient. Instead, it is essential to also monitor the core temperature of the irradiated material.

Not only temperature gradients existed on the level of the catalyst bed, the edges and contact points of each pellet were approximately 100 °C hotter than the rest of the object. This tendency for contact points to reach higher temperatures was previously reported by Haneishi et al. [23] for spherical particles.

These observations regard only to the pellets located at the reactor wall, as it is not possible to directly assess the thermal response of those located deeper within the reactor. However, based on the findings of Haneishi [23], a similar phenomenon is likely to occur within the reactor, potentially leading to the formation of diffuse hotspots throughout the entire microwave-exposed volume.

Table 2 summarizes the microwave energy consumption and the temperature gradients during reforming for the different experiments. Several observations can be made regarding the power data: The adsorbed power is much higher than the heat consumption needed to heat up the reaction mixture and the endothermic reaction. An estimate of the maximum heat consumed by the dry reforming reaction at 300 mL/min at 850 °C over the powder catalyst ($X = 0.65$) is 7 Watt. To heat 300 mL/min gas from 25 – 850 °C approximately 7 Watt is needed. Thus,

Fig. 9. Heating and dry reforming over powder catalyst at 750 °C with a total flow of 300 mL/min in the microwave heated reactor.

Table 2

Microwave power consumption and temperature gradient between the center of the catalyst bed and the reactor wall during dry reforming.

sample	total power	absorbed power	reflected power	T _{center} - T _{wall}
Ni/SiC pellet 850 °C	215 W	124 W (58 %)	91 W (42 %)	185 °C
Ni/SiC pellet 750 °C	166 W	101 W (61 %)	65 W (39 %)	160 °C
Ni/SiC powder 850 °C	139 W	93 W (67 %)	46 W (33 %)	178 °C
Ni/SiC powder 750 °C	122 W	84 W (69 %)	38 W (31 %)	154 °C

mainly heat losses determine the net adsorbed microwave power consumption. Temperature gradients between the reactor center and the wall depend on the center bed temperature and are similar for both powders and pellets. The adsorbed microwave power consumption is much higher for the pellets than for the powder catalyst. Due to the larger voids the heat loss by radiation for the pellets is much higher than that for the powder catalyst, leading to higher microwave power consumption.

4. Conclusions

Evaluation of catalyst performance at lab scale by microwave heating is almost always carried out in quartz reactors. Due to radiation losses through the quartz wall, strong radial temperature gradients will occur. These radial temperature gradients are the inverse of those occurring in a reactor heated by an external furnace. This makes comparison of fixed bed catalytic performance data between microwave and furnace heated reactors almost always flawed.

5 wt. % Ni/SiC catalyst in both powder and pellet form show good catalytic activity, but limited long-term stability. Both samples can be heated easily by microwave radiation to 750 - 850 °C. Although the penetration depth of the microwaves at 2.45 GHz at 800 °C is approximately 1 cm, a temperature gradient is observed on the 2 mm x 2 mm cylindrical pellets. The edges are hotter than the bulk of the pellet under inert and reactive flow conditions.

The radial temperature gradients observed in this study are mainly

due to radiation losses through the transparent quartz reactor wall. Isolation of the reactor or using a material that is less transparent for IR radiation will significantly reduce these temperature gradients. In that case temperature measurements become more difficult as an external IR camera can no longer be used.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Andrea Merlo: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Léon Thomann:** Investigation, Data curation. **Yuna Han:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Emmanuel Landrison:** Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Nolven Guilhaume:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration. **Yves Schuurman:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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